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Frequency dependence of sensitivity to interaural phase differences in pure tones

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ABSTRACT:

It is well established that in normal-hearing humans, the threshold of interaural time differences for pure tones increases dramatically above about 1300 Hz, only to become unmeasurable above 1400 Hz. However, physiological data and auditory models suggest that the actual decline in sensitivity is more gradual and only appears to be abrupt because the maximum of the psychometric function dips below the threshold proportion correct, e.g., 0.794. Published data only report thresholds at certain proportions correct but not the decline of proportions correct or of the sensitivity index d' with increasing frequencies. Here, we present pure-tone behavioral data obtained with a constant stimulus procedure. Seven of nine subjects showed proportions correct above 0.9 at 1300 Hz and virtually no sensitivity at 1500 Hz (proportion correct within 0.07 of chance level). This corresponds to a sensitivity decline of 46–78 dB/oct, much steeper than predicted by existing models or by the decline of phase locking of the auditory nerve fibers in animal data.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Binaural cues provide humans with the ability to discriminate azimuthal angles of sound direction. The cue that enables the discrimination of angles as small as 1° is the interaural time difference (ITD) in the temporal fine structure (TFS) (Mills, 1958), abbreviated here as ITD-FS. To measure human sensitivity to ITD-FS in isolation, pure-tone presentation via headphones is necessary. Usually, two intervals are used with the same magnitude of ITD but with opposite signs (i.e., $ITD_2 = -ITD_1$) (Brughera *et al.*, 2013). Sensitivity is then often reported as the ΔITD threshold:

$$\Delta ITD = ITD_1 - ITD_2 = 2 ITD, \quad (1)$$

with $ITD = |ITD_1| = |ITD_2|$, i.e., the difference in ITD between two successive sounds at which a certain proportion correct (e.g., $p_c = 0.794$) is achieved. Previous studies have underlined the remarkable ITD-FS sensitivity of trained normal-hearing subjects. The maximum sensitivity, i.e., the lowest ΔITD thresholds for pure-tone sensitivity, have consistently been reported for frequencies of 700–1000 Hz, where the thresholds can be as low as 10–30 μs (Brughera *et al.*, 2013; Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956).

However, despite the remarkably low thresholds at low frequencies, ITD sensitivity deteriorates rapidly for frequencies above 1 kHz and $p_c = 0.794$ thresholds become unmeasurable above 1.4 kHz (Brughera *et al.*, 2013). This sudden

increase in ΔITD thresholds is called upper frequency limit of ITD-FS sensitivity. The thresholds only provide a single data point for the unknown psychometric function $p(f, \Delta ITD)$. Further, there is no information about sensitivity above 1.4 kHz.

The upper frequency limit of ITD-FS perception has been related to the upper limit of phase locking of auditory nerve (AN) fibers to the TFS in humans (Verschooten *et al.*, 2019). Synchrony index (SI) is the most-used metric for phase locking, also referred to as vector strength (Goldberg and Brown, 1969). Phase-locking data of AN fibers are only available for non-human animals, but interesting common features emerge when comparing data from different mammalian species (Johnson, 1980; Kiang *et al.*, 1965; Rose *et al.*, 1967). The decline of SI across frequency has a very similar shape and steepness across species, but the corner frequency varies when expressed as a low-pass filter (Weiss and Rose, 1988a). For all mammalian species for which data are available, there is still a highly significant phase locking at 1.4 kHz which, at higher frequencies, declines at approximately 18–19 dB/oct (Verschooten *et al.*, 2015; Weiss and Rose, 1988a, 1988b). Phenomenological models of human ITD perception commonly explicitly include such a low-pass filter, which can correctly simulate the reduced binaural unmasking with increasing frequency (Breebaart *et al.*, 2001b). However, such filters do not accurately simulate the abrupt increase in pure tone threshold ITDs (Bouse *et al.*, 2019; Breebaart *et al.*, 2001b).

The discrepancy between the models and experimental data (Brughera *et al.*, 2013) is not particularly striking below 1.4 kHz. Yet, the models can, of course, provide simulations

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also at higher frequencies: Bouse *et al.* (2019) simulate a $p_c = 0.794$ threshold of $160 \mu\text{s}$ at 1.45 kHz . Using a lower $p_c = 0.707$, Breebaart *et al.* (2001b) are even able to simulate a threshold of $50 \mu\text{s}$ at 1.5 kHz . However, as no experimental data exist, it is unclear whether the maximum possible human p_c at 1.45 and 1.5 kHz is just marginally lower or far below the threshold proportions of 0.794 or 0.707 , respectively. To determine the ITD sensitivity roll-off experimentally, the p_c must be measured directly to estimate how it changes over frequency for a fixed ΔITD . In Sec. II, basic concepts of signal detection theory are reviewed and used to propose a basic model of the psychometric function.

The goals of the present study are (1) to provide the currently missing psychophysical data on ITD-FS sensitivity in the frequency range between 1300 and 1500 Hz , (2) to extract and describe the slope of ITD-FS sensitivity in terms of the sensitivity index (d' , “d prime”), with a focus on the 1300 – 1500 Hz frequency range, and (3) to relate existing models and concepts to the low-pass characteristic.

II. MODEL OF THE PSYCHOMETRIC FUNCTION

In signal detection theory, the sensitivity of sensory systems in different psychophysical tasks is often quantified with the sensitivity index d' (Green and Swets, 1966). A principal assumption thereby is that the various sensory events (triggered by a stimulus) can be mapped to a single dimension of experimental interest. Each observation (of the target or the reference) produces one event on this dimension. Consequently, the stimuli are represented as two partially overlapping distributions. For ITD discrimination in a two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) paradigm, it is assumed that the subject compares the internal laterality representation of the first interval to the representation of the second interval. d' is considered as the ideal observer performance

$$d' = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\sigma} = \frac{\Delta\mu}{\sigma}, \tag{2}$$

where μ_1 and μ_2 are the means of the distributions of the internal representation and σ is the standard deviation of each distribution (assuming both standard deviations are reasonably similar). Further, the distributions are assumed to be Gaussian, so the discrimination index can be transformed to a discrimination probability p in a 2AFC experiment by

$$p = \Phi\left(\frac{d'}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \tag{3}$$

with Φ the normal cumulative distribution function. This transformation is done implicitly throughout the text.

Psychophysically, it cannot be distinguished whether a change in sensitivity is caused by a change of $\Delta\mu$ or by a change of σ of the internal representation. That, however, provides the freedom to assign all acoustic differences between target and reference waveform to the numerator $\Delta\mu$ and all differences caused by the processing of the auditory

system to the denominator σ . Regarding the acoustical difference, the two intervals differ in their interaural phase difference (IPD) and the magnitude of the difference is ΔIPD . The maximum physical difference in phase space is 180° or π rads. In the present case with $\text{IPD}_1 = -\text{IPD}_2$, the maximum (π) difference for ΔIPD occurs for a nominal IPD of $\pi/2$ rads only to become zero again at an IPD of π . The acoustical difference $\Delta\mu$ can thus be expressed as

$$\Delta\mu := \sin(\text{IPD}). \tag{4}$$

With this definition, the remaining term $1/\sigma$ becomes a measure of observer sensitivity and Eq. (2) can be rewritten as

$$d'(f, \Delta\text{IPD}) = \frac{\sin(\text{IPD})}{\sigma(f, \text{IPD})}. \tag{5}$$

The focus of this study is describing d' , or better, the observer sensitivity $1/\sigma$, as a function of frequency. To compare this function to the decline of phase locking and to the low-pass filter of the models, the final quantity of interest is the slope of $1/\sigma(f)$. To compare the slope across different modalities and units (neural synchrony index, vs model filter, vs psychophysically obtained sensitivity index) changes of all quantities are expressed in decibels. The resulting slope unit is dB/oct and thus expresses the decline while the frequency doubles. Therefore, a \log_2 frequency transformation is necessary to obtain slope m from linearly fitting d' :

$$10 \log_{10}(d'(f)) = -m \log_2(f/\text{Hz}) + b. \tag{6}$$

We calculated the least squares solution for m , with b as a second free parameter determining the y axis intercept in this linear fit, which is not used for further analysis.

The slope m in Brughera *et al.* (2013) behavioral data can be predicted by combining Eqs. (5) and (6) (see Appendix, Sec. 2). When applied to the data of Brughera *et al.* (2013), the slope estimates from this dataset range from 30 – 76 dB/oct , depending on frequency range and subject. Thus, a further motivation for this study is to test whether Eq. (5) provides a valid basis for the psychometric function and whether the estimation of the slope is confirmed by Experiment II in Sec. V.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Subjects

Subjects were limited to young adults with audiometric thresholds $\leq 15 \text{ dB}$ hearing level (HL) at octave-spaced frequencies from 125 – 6000 Hz . The interaural asymmetry in audiometric threshold was $\leq 10 \text{ dB}$ at all of the frequencies tested. Since Bernstein and Trahiotis (2016) found a significant dependence of dichotic detection thresholds on the audiometric thresholds at 4 kHz , a maximum audiometric threshold of 5 dB HL at this frequency was an additional criterion for the subjects. Nine normal-hearing trained subjects between 21 and 29 years of age (average age = 27 , females = 3 , men = 6) participated in the experiment.

FIG. 1. Psychometric functions and fits. The nine rows show proportion correct (p_c) over ΔIPD of the nine subjects (S1–S9). Different frequencies are shown in different columns. The error bars denote the 95% confidence level derived from the binomial distribution. Therefore, the confidence interval size depends on the p_c and on the number of times measured (N). Since an adaptive method was used, N varies with subject and condition. Only data from ΔIPDs presented at least 48 times during the 16 adaptive tracks are plotted. The solid lines represent the fit with free parameter σ as given by values in the panel corners.

The duration of the measurements was 15–20 h per subject, performed in a different number of sessions for each subject. Within a session (45 min to 2 h), subjects could take unlimited breaks. Two of the nine subjects were laboratory members and were well informed about the purpose and methods of the study. They did not receive extra compensation whereas the other subjects were paid. The study was approved by the Ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg.

B. Procedure

The procedure was a two-interval, two-alternative forced-choice task (2I-2AFC). The subject had to respond to indicate whether the tone in the second interval was perceived to the left or the right of that presented in the first interval. The stimuli had synchronous onset and offset gating in both ears, so that the tones differed only in their IPD, i.e., their ongoing ITD-FS.

Tones were presented to the subject via Sennheiser (Wedemark, Hanover, Germany) HD-650 headphones at 70

dB SPL. Levels were measured with a sound-level meter and an artificial ear type 4153 (Brüel & Kjær, Virum, Denmark). Digital-analog conversion was carried out by ADI-s DAC FS (RME, Haimhausen, Germany) with 32 bit and a 48 kHz sampling rate. Stimuli were generated digitally using the AFC-software package (Ewert, 2013, Oldenburg, Germany). The subjects were seated in a double-walled, sound-attenuating booth and responded by pressing a key on a standard computer keyboard. Visual feedback was provided after each trial. The 300 ms tone duration included 50 ms \cos^2 rise-decay ramps. A 50 ms silent interval separated the two intervals. A next pair of intervals was presented 500 ms after the subject responded.

The interaural difference of the stimuli presented in the two intervals was symmetrical around zero (Brughera *et al.*, 2013; Hafter *et al.*, 1979; Henning, 1983; Thavam and Dietz, 2019), so that in one of the two intervals, the right ear was leading; in the other, the left ear led by the same IPD. Subjects could thus make their decision based on a ΔIPD difference between the two intervals.

FIG. 2. The nine panels portray the proportion correct (p_c) of the nine subjects (S1–S9). Error bars denote the 95% confidence level. Symbols denote different frequencies as show in the legend on the top. Only S6 has data for 1200 Hz.

While the focus of this study was on the frequency range ≥ 1300 Hz, Sec. IV will elaborate on Experiment I, where we performed measurements in the frequency range from 250–1200 Hz. In Experiment II, we address the primary aim of this study—to derive the slope of sensitivity decline across frequency by measuring with constant Δ IPDs in the frequency range of 1300–1500 Hz. To obtain a fine frequency resolution, a 50 Hz spacing was used; details are provided in Sec. V. (See supplementary material for audio-grams and results for all subjects.¹)

IV. EXPERIMENT I

Sensitivity to low-frequency pure tones is a fundamental aspect of binaural hearing. Therefore, the first purpose of Experiment I was to provide a comprehensive dataset for future reference or analysis. Previous studies mostly focused on the frequency dependence of threshold ITDs at a certain p_c value (e.g., Brughera *et al.*, 2013; Zwislocki and Feldman, 1956). We chose an adaptive staircase procedure to collect most responses well above chance and well below ceiling performance. We then display and analyze the proportions correct at all Δ IPDs included during the adaptive runs, not the typically reported threshold ITDs.

Measuring well below the frequency limit means measuring at small IPDs. For reference IPDs from 0 to $\pi/4$ rads,

sensitivity to changes in IPD (i.e., to Δ IPD) is best and reasonably independent of the reference IPD (Yost, 1974). The second purpose of Experiment I was to test whether $\sigma(f, \text{IPD})$ can be assumed to be IPD-independent up to $\pi/4$ rads, i.e., up to Δ IPD = $\pi/2$ rads. If this is the case, then d' is proportional to $\sin(\text{IPD})$ [see. Eq. (5)]. In other words, for each subject and each frequency, the psychometric function $p_c(\Delta$ IPD) can then be fitted with a single free parameter σ .

A. Measurement table

In Experiment I, different fixed frequencies (250, 500, 650, 800, 1000, 1100, 1200 Hz) were presented. For each frequency, an adaptive “three-down, one-up” staircase procedure controlled the Δ IPD, i.e., the Δ IPD was decreased after three correct responses in a row and increased after each incorrect response, asymptoting a p_c of 0.794 (Levitt, 1971). Each adaptive track started at a Δ IPD of 0.23 π rads. This starting value was selected based on the results of a pilot experiment, where it resulted in proportions correct well over 0.9. The initial step size was a factor of 2, which was reduced to 1.414 and 1.189 after the first and second “down-up-reversal.” An adaptive track was terminated after 10 reversals at the minimum step size. Starting at 250 Hz, the tone frequency was increased after each track, up to 1200 Hz, and then decreased after a second track at

1200 Hz. This sequence was repeated 8 times, resulting in 16 adaptive tracks per frequency.

B. Results with fitted psychometric functions

The usual threshold calculation by reversals was omitted. For each combination of frequency and ΔIPD , the p_c was calculated. Although the number of presentations N varied due to the adaptive procedure, it typically exceeded $N = 200$ near the threshold, corresponding to $p_c = 0.794$. This is reflected by the error bars in Fig. 1 denoting the 95% confidence intervals (Johnson *et al.*, 1993). The psychometric functions shown as solid lines in Fig. 1 indicate a fit based on Eq. (5) (d' to p_c and ΔIPD to IPD transformation applied), with the free parameter σ to all responses from the 16 runs for each frequency and subject. Alternatively, a different σ -value can be derived for each data point, i.e., for each ΔIPD . We did not find a trend in these values over the fairly small ΔIPD range, and the IPD-independent σ results in good fits for all frequencies and subjects. The maximum likelihood fit was derived by a grid search with steps of 0.001 from 0.001–0.8. Details about the likelihood function and the merge over ΔIPD can be found in the Appendix [see Eqs. (A1) and (A3)]. The resulting ITD thresholds are shown in Sec. VII A.

V. EXPERIMENT II

A. Measurement table

In Experiment II, different fixed frequencies (1300, 1350, 1400, 1450, and 1500 Hz) were presented in combination with fixed $\Delta IPDs$ (0.1 π , 0.2 π , 0.4 π , 0.6 π , 0.8 π , 1.0 π , 1.2 π , and 1.4 π , rads). We chose a constant stimulus procedure to get the same number of repetitions for conditions with high and low p_c . The small differences in sensitivity across subjects during the pilot-testing phase led us to decide for this approach. Not all possible combinations were measured: for example, as the performance for $f \geq 1450$ Hz was near chance level in the pilot experiment, we only measured at ΔIPD of 0.4 π rad and 1 π rad at those highest frequencies. Each combination was presented in blocks of 50 trials. The frequency was changed upwards from 1300 Hz, then downwards from 1500 Hz after all $\Delta IPDs$ had been presented in descending order. In total, 56

blocks (28 conditions) were measured four times for each ΔIPD ; thus, at each frequency resulting in 400 trials per combination. Subject 6 was not able to achieve $p_c > 0.7$ for 1300 Hz; thus, the performance was additionally measured for 1200 Hz, but not for 1450 and 1500 Hz.

B. Results

Figure 2 displays the p_c across ΔIPD for the different frequencies. The panels of the figure each contain data for one of 9 different subjects. Error bars represent the 95% confidence intervals (Johnson *et al.*, 1993). Three phenomena stand out in the data:

- (1) Nearly all subjects (7 of 9) show performance of $p_c > 0.9$ at 1300 Hz, which drops within a 15% frequency increase (2.5 semitones) to $p_c < 0.6$ at 1500 Hz.
- (2) In general, performance increased with ΔIPD until $\Delta IPD = 0.8\pi$ rad, beyond which performance started to decrease.

C. Effect of IPD on sensitivity

The dependence of the performance on IPD is reflected in the course of sensitivity in Fig. 2. Within these data, ΔIPD ranges from 0.1–1.4 π rads which allows us to analyze $\sigma(f, IPD)$. It is not possible to collect these data with the symmetric paradigm at lower frequencies, due to ceiling performance.

The largest stimulus difference between both intervals is at a $\Delta IPD = \pi$ rads but the highest proportions correct are usually at a lower ΔIPD . We interpret this as an indication of an increase in σ with IPD.

We aim to characterize the increasing internal processing uncertainty σ towards π rads, i.e., towards $\Delta IPD = 2\pi$ rads. This is done by fitting a periodic function to $\sigma(IPD)$ and investigating the fit parameters. Based on Yost (1974), we constrained the function to have a minimum σ_0 (highest sensitivity) at $IPD = 0$ and a maximum at $IPD = \pi$ rads. A simple *ad hoc* choice for such a function with one additional parameter is

$$\sigma(IPD) = g [1 - \cos(IPD)] + \sigma_0, \tag{7}$$

with g as a measure of the magnitude of the IPD dependence. For better visualization, we excluded the frequency

FIG. 3. Illustration of the psychometric function. (A) Stimulus difference between target and reference, cf. Eq. (4). (B) Three examples of Eq. (7) using values 0, 0.2, and 0.4 for the parameter g , expressing the IPD dependence of the IPD sensitivity. The measure σ is inversely related to IPD sensitivity. (C) Resulting psychometric functions expressed as sensitivity index $d' = \Delta\mu/\sigma$, cf. Eq. (2). (D) Same as (C) but transformed into proportion correct (p_c) by Eq. (3). The psychometric functions differ from the typical sigmoidal shape because of the linear x axis and the periodicity of ΔIPD .

FIG. 4. (Color online) Proportions correct from Fig. 2 transformed to d' (only for frequencies with more than two data points). Additionally, the fitted psychometric functions from Eq. (8) are plotted for each frequency and subject.

dependence for σ , σ_0 and g from Eq. (7). Figure 3(B) shows $\sigma(\text{IPD})$ for three different values of g . Their influences on sensitivity are shown in Figs. 3(C) and 3(D). We propose this descriptive model for the IPD sensitivity index:

$$\hat{d}'(\Delta\text{IPD}) = \frac{\Delta\mu(\Delta\text{IPD})}{\sigma(\Delta\text{IPD})} = \frac{\sin(\text{IPD})}{g[1 - \cos(\text{IPD})] + \sigma_0}. \quad (8)$$

Again, a grid search was used to determine the parameters g (steps of 0.1 from 0–3) and σ_0 (steps of 0.1 from 0.1–0.8), which maximized the likelihood. The resulting functions for all stimulus conditions and subjects are displayed in Fig. 4 as solid lines.

VI. ANALYSIS OF THE FREQUENCY DEPENDENCE

With the data and the fitted psychometric functions, we were able to analyze IPD sensitivity as a function of frequency. Our foremost interest is the slope of the sensitivity decline, i.e., of $d'(f)$. In Fig. 5, the sensitivity index for different ΔIPDs is shown as a function of frequency. Those data were already shown as functions of ΔIPD in Fig. 4 and are now re-plotted as functions of f . We can directly use these d' values to estimate their slope across frequency. Alternatively, we can use the σ values, depending on σ_0 and g , which were independently optimized (via maximum likelihood) for each frequency, from the previous fitted psychometric functions since $d' \sim 1/\sigma$. In the following, we will

elaborate on the two ways to quantify the slope of d' with respect to frequency.

A. Likelihood fit on frequency dependence for specific ΔIPD

The slope m in Eq. (6) is directly fitted to the sensitivity index as a function of frequency for a specific ΔIPD and subject. Again, a grid search was used to maximize the likelihood. The slope m ranges from 6–140 dB/oct in steps of 1 dB/oct. Since a higher slope requires a higher intersection b , we set $b = mc$ where c ranges from 9.3–10.6 in steps of 0.0025. The solid lines in the nine panels for the subjects of Fig. 5 represent the functions resulting in the maximum likelihood and the solutions for m are shown in the lowest right panel in Fig. 5 for the nine subjects. Especially for the ΔIPDs with the most data points (0.4 and 1π), the slopes are most consistent across subjects, resulting in 95% confidence intervals of 53–70 and 46–66 dB/oct, respectively. This shows the importance of the data points at 1450 and 1500 Hz in confining the slope estimate. Brughera *et al.* (2013) related a specific centroid measure of their model to a threshold to account for their data. Thus, we were able to scale their measure to d' and calculate the decline across frequency (see Appendix, Sec. 3). The d' decline over frequency from the centroid model (Brughera *et al.*, 2013)

FIG. 5. (Color online) Δ IPD-specific estimates of the frequency dependence of d' . Panels S1–S9: Symbols represent the d' values for different Δ IPDs across frequency of subjects S1–S9. The error bars denote the 95% confidence intervals. Solid lines show the maximum likelihood fit obtained from Eq. (6), see Sec. VI A. d' prediction of the centroid model is depicted by the dashed black line (Brughera et al., 2013). Bottom right: Slope m of $d'(f)$ for different Δ IPDs for the nine different subjects marked in symbols. The numbers below the symbols state data from how many frequencies were available for the fitting at the respective Δ IPD. The dashed black line represents the prediction of the centroid model.

(dotted black line, 20 dB/oct) is too shallow to explain the sensitivity measured in this experiment.

B. Least-square fit on derived psychometric functions

As the slope of d' across frequency does not greatly depend on Δ IPD, the second approach is to derive a single slope value for each subject, combining data from a different Δ IPD. Equation (7) depicts the influence of the IPD on σ . To fit an IPD-independent slope, we derived the mean value of σ over Δ IPD, which is

$$\bar{\sigma}(f) = \sigma_0(f) + g(f) = \sigma(f, \pi/2) \quad (9)$$

and is depicted in Fig. 6(A). We used $d' = 1/\bar{\sigma}(f)$ with $f \geq 1300$ Hz [see example data in Fig. 6(B)] to compute the least-square solution of m in Eq. (6), which is shown in Fig. 6(C) for the nine subjects. The 95% confidence interval of the slope across subjects is 53–78 dB/oct.

Both ways to calculate the slope across frequency clearly show that for all subjects, it is greater than 30 dB/oct [see Fig. 6(C) and Fig. 5 (bottom right)] and the confidence intervals are mostly overlapping with an overall range of 46–78 dB/oct.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. ITD thresholds

To compare our behavioral results and the fitted psychometric functions to previous behavioral data, we calculated the Δ IPD thresholds ($p_c = 0.794 \Rightarrow d' = 1.16$) numerically from the best-fit psychometric functions and plotted the respective Δ ITD thresholds in Fig. 7. Compared to previously published data also shown in Fig. 7, the thresholds reported in the present study at 250 Hz are lower for most subjects, but somewhat higher around 800 Hz. Consequently, while previously published thresholds decline with a frequency increase from 250 up to about 800 Hz, our data are better described by a broad plateau ranging from 500–800 Hz and sometimes even to 1100 Hz. Although we do not have a good explanation for this deviation, Brughera et al. (2013) reported that small changes in their procedure, e.g., the choice of test frequencies, influenced the decline. Minor procedural differences that we consider unlikely to cause the difference are (1) the duration of 300 ms with 50 ms ramps compared to 500 ms duration with 100 ms ramps (Brughera et al., 2013) and (2) that we used multiplicative step sizes in our adaptive procedure. The overall magnitude of thresholds and their steep increase above 1.2 kHz is in line with previously published data (see Fig. 7).

FIG. 6. (Color online) Mean values of the fitted σ values and their slope with respect to frequency. (A) Range of σ for all subjects across frequency (gray area), and for some representative subjects [color code in (C)] selected to span the range of performance. (B) Symbols represent the same values as in (A) [color code in (C)], and solid lines represent the least squares linear fit to the data for $f \geq 1300$ Hz. (C) Slope of the linear fit in (B). The error bars denote the 95% confidence intervals.

B. IPD dependence of sensitivity

There is a difference between the Δ IPD for the largest stimulus difference between both intervals, and where subjects gained the maximal correct proportion. Maximal sensitivity at Δ IPD $< \pi$ rads is in agreement with observations made by Yost (1974) who reported increasing thresholds with increasing reference IPD towards π rads. It also fits with the IPD dependence of Fisher information extracted from a population of ITD-sensitive neurons typical for mammals (Pavão *et al.*, 2020).

C. Steepness of IPD sensitivity decline

The results quantify the previously reported sudden reduction of ITD-FS sensitivity from $f = 1300$ Hz to $f = 1500$ Hz to be 9.5–16 dB. This corresponds to a d' -slope m of 46–78 dB/oct which is close to the decline derived from the behavioral data of Brughera *et al.* (2013) when assuming Eq. (5) (see Appendix, Sec. 2). Such a steep decline is outstanding in psychoacoustics and is not assumed or reproduced by any model. In the following paragraphs, we discuss mechanisms that may contribute to the decline, and are partially already implemented in existing models.

As described in the Introduction, the reduction in sensitivity is commonly associated with the loss of synchrony of the AN to the TFS towards higher frequencies. Joris and Verschooten (2013) and Verschooten *et al.* (2019) directly connected the upper frequency limit of AN phase locking with the upper frequency limit of ITD-FS sensitivity, and thus expect the limit of phase locking in humans to be near 1400 Hz. Many phenomenological models of binaural processing include a low-pass filter to model the loss of

synchrony of AN input (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 1996; Bouse *et al.*, 2019; Breebaart *et al.*, 2001a, 2001b; Dietz *et al.*, 2009). The order of the filter is often taken from physiological studies. As the biophysical mechanisms causing the synchrony decline are arguably the same across species, the steepness is indeed very consistent across different species (Weiss and Rose, 1988a) and there is no reason to assume a different steepness in humans. The species-dependent corner frequency is then used as a free parameter to fit a model to human data (e.g., Bernstein and Trahiotis, 1996). Breebaart *et al.* (2001a, 2001b) employed a cascade of five 1st-order low-pass filters with a resulting corner frequency at 770 Hz. In contrast to a single 5th-order low-pass filter, the cascaded design has a more gradual transition to maximum steepness and thus only 2 dB attenuation in the frequency interval 1300–1500 Hz. Therefore, their model still predicts low threshold ITDs at 1.5 kHz. This modest decline is in contrast to the steep ITD-FS sensitivity decline observed in the present study and to the data from Brughera *et al.* (2013). It can thus be concluded that additional effects must cause the steep decline of ITD-FS sensitivity. The next processing stage is the anteroventral cochlear nucleus (AVCN), which receives input from the AN and projects into the medial superior olive (MSO), where the first binaural interaction takes place. AVCN neurons preserve and further enhance the precision of temporal information in the neural firing of the AN (Joris *et al.*, 1994; Pickles, 2015). Yet, the asymptotic synchrony decline across frequency in Joris *et al.* (1994) is even somewhat shallower than the average decline in AN fibers. Therefore, processing in the AVCN does not appear to contribute to the steeper roll-off of ITD-FS sensitivity.

- ▼ Zwislocky & Feldmann 1956 ◁ Brughera et. al 2013 L1 ● S1 ◀ S6
- Klumpp & Eady 1956 ▷ Brughera et. al 2013 L2 ▼ S2 ★ S7
- ⋯ Dye 1990 S1 ◁ Brughera et. al 2013 L3 ◆ S3 ◀ S8
- ⋯* Dye 1990 S2 ▷ Brughera et. al 2013 L4 ▼ S4 ★ S9
- Bernstein & Trahiotis 2002 ◆ Thavam & Dietz 2019 ■ S5

FIG. 7. (Color online) Threshold Δ ITDs corresponding to $d' = 1.16$ ($p_c = 0.794$) from subjects S1–S9. Additionally, threshold Δ ITDs are shown for previous datasets (Bernstein and Trahiotis, 2002; Klumpp and Eady, 1956; Dye, 1990).

Processing of the inputs within the MSO could be another origin of the decline of ITD-FS sensitivity across frequency. Even if its inputs were perfectly phase locked, the duration of the input conductance imposes a frequency limitation on ITD sensitivity. The excitatory postsynaptic potential or the coincidence-detection window acts as an additional low-pass filter. This low-pass characteristic is also reflected in the modulation depth of the Brughera *et al.* (2013) model rate ITD functions (already including the AVCN decline), declining by 3 dB between 1250 and 1500 Hz, i.e., a decline of about 2.4 dB can be expected in the 1300–1500 Hz interval. This decline is 1.4 dB more than the AVCN phase-locking decline of their model within this interval. Bouse *et al.* (2019) used the peripheral filter from Breebaart *et al.* (2001a) and include an additional low-pass filter within their MSO model. Between 1300 and 1500 Hz, the ITD-FS sensitivity of their model declines by 4 dB.

A common model approach for ITD encoding relies on an array of binaural coincidence-detecting neurons receiving differently delayed inputs from the left and right ear (Jeffress, 1948). Such a coincidence-detecting model unit responds maximally when the relative internal delay

between its bilateral inputs exactly compensates for the external ITD. Based on this delay-line approach, binaural perception has commonly been modeled and explained by interaural cross correlation (Colburn, 1977; Jeffress, 1948; Lindemann, 1986; Stern and Shear, 1996). To investigate this hypothesis, Brughera *et al.* (2013) examined the increase in the ITD-FS thresholds across frequency with several model types, including a delay-line model (Jeffress, 1948) simulated as a delay-weighted (centroid) cross correlation (Stern and Colburn, 1978). With increasing frequency, the number of cross correlation cycles falling into the strongly weighted delay range increases as well. As the weight of the first negative side-peak increases (with increasing ITD), it counteracts the primary peak, i.e., the one corresponding to the nominal ITD. This causes low-pass filtering and is one limitation of ITD-FS sensitivity in this model. The sensitivity roll-off obtained with the model by Brughera *et al.* (2013) after centroid threshold calculation (thus including SI decline of AVCN and MSO low-pass filter) corresponds to a 4.2 dB attenuation for d' between 1300 and 1500 Hz. The p_c for the threshold IPD at 1400 Hz is 0.79 and would be 0.69 and 0.62 at 1500 and 1600 Hz,

respectively. To our knowledge, this is the model with the steepest ITD-FS sensitivity decline, but it is still far too gradual to account for the present data.

To summarize, the phase locking of AN fibers declines relatively gradually (18–19 dB/oct), as does the simulated ITD sensitivity of auditory models (≤ 21 dB/oct). On the other hand, the ITD sensitivity index of our subjects declines in a narrow interval between 1300 and 1500 Hz by 46–78 dB/oct, unparalleled in psychoacoustics. This discrepancy shows that we do not yet fully understand the effects that lead to this steep decline. It is possible that the upper limit of phase locking in humans is at considerably higher frequencies (Moore, 2021; Verschooten *et al.*, 2019) and factors other than phase locking are the primary cause of the frequency limitation of ITD sensitivity.

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APPENDIX

1. Maximum likelihood fit

For the fitting in Secs. IV B, V C, and VI A, we used the following functions. To describe how well the observed k of N (proportion correct – p_c) fit to the probability p , the binomial probability mass function serves as a likelihood function, where the likelihood is maximal if $p = p_c$:

$$l = b(k, N, p) = \binom{N}{k} p^k (1 - p)^{N-k}, \tag{A1}$$

with k the number of correct choices from N presentations. The likelihood function in Eq. (A1) describes the “goodness of fit” of the probability p for a single pair of k correct answers of N presentations. The likelihood for a series of these pairs is calculated by Eq. (A2). Since these values could become small, and are not guaranteed to be numerically stable, the log-likelihood is used Eq. (A3):

$$l = \prod_{j=1}^J b(k_j, N_j, \hat{p}_j), \tag{A2}$$

$$\log(l) = \sum_{j=1}^J \log(b(k_j, N_j, \hat{p}_j)), \tag{A3}$$

with j the index of data points and J the number of data points.

2. Sensitivity decline over frequency for a fixed IPD of the behavioral data by Brughera *et al.* (2013)

Brughera *et al.* (2013) reported threshold values for pure tones across frequency. These values show how Δ IPD changes for a fixed d' and are shown for their Listener 1 in Fig. 8(A) as a solid black line. However, the goal in this study is to get the slope of how d' changes over a fixed Δ IPD. Therefore, a description of the psychometric function

FIG. 8. (Color online) (A) Threshold Δ IPD corresponding to $d' = 1.16$ from Listener 1 (Brughera *et al.*, 2013) across frequency and predictions from the centroid model [Brughera *et al.*, 2013, Fig. 6(A)]. The three markers represent the thresholds for 1300, 1350, and 1400 Hz. (B) The psychometric function in Eq. (5) was matched to the threshold values from (A) by fitting σ for each frequency (solid lines). The vertical dotted line indicates $d' = 1.16$. The dashed lines represent the psychometric function for 1450 and 1500 Hz assuming the decline of σ across frequency continues by -62 dB/oct. (C) Output from centroid model in (Brughera *et al.*, 2013, Fig. 5). The horizontal dashed line (9 μ s) marks the threshold criterion and thus relates to $d' = 1.16$. The intercepts with this line are equivalent with the threshold model predictions in (A). Despite the fact that the unit of the x-axis of this plot is IPD, Brughera *et al.* (2013) used this metric to derive Δ IPD thresholds from the intercepts. This results in a factor of 2 error in the threshold estimates. The corrected (multiplication by two) predictions are plotted in (A) as dashed line.

is needed. Fitting Eq. (5) (with σ depending only on frequency) to the threshold values from Brughera *et al.* (2013) results in different sensitivity values (d') across frequency. The values of σ that provide the best fit to the thresholds at the three highest frequencies where thresholds were measurable in Brughera *et al.* (2013) for Listener 1, are shown in Fig. 8(B). Obviously, the frequency range of considered data points influences the slope estimate. The focus of the present study is on the maximum slope that can be expected near the highest frequencies at which IPD sensitivity can be measured. The trade-off is that a too small interval and a fit at too high test frequencies increases the uncertainty of the slope estimate. A too large fit interval may result in an underestimation of the maximum slope. For example, the three data points from 1300–1400 Hz of their Listener 1 in Brughera *et al.* (2013) yield a slope of $m \approx 62$ dB/oct. Excluding the data point at 1300 Hz, yield a slope of $m \approx 66$ dB/oct, while including the data point at 1250 Hz yield a slope of $m \approx 54$ dB/oct. Depending on frequency range and subject, the sensitivity slope ranged from 30–76 dB/oct.

3. Sensitivity decline over frequency for a fixed IPD of the centroid model

Brughera *et al.* (2013) used a delay-line model (Jeffress, 1948) simulated as a delay-weighted (centroid) cross correlation (Stern and Colburn, 1978) to predict the ITD thresholds from their experiment. The rate ITD functions $c(\tau)$ of the coincidence-detecting model units are represented by the four parameter equation in Appendix B in Brughera *et al.* (2013). Values for the four parameters are reported for a set of frequencies. We did a linear interpolation for these values to obtain solutions for frequencies between 1300–1500 Hz. To calculate the centroid measure, the density-weighted cross correlation (Brughera *et al.*, 2013) [Eq. (5)] was used:

$$\bar{\tau}(\Delta t) = \frac{\int p(\tau)\tau c(\tau - \Delta t) d\tau}{\int p(\tau)c(\tau - \Delta t) d\tau}, \quad (A4)$$

with the density function $p(\tau)$ from (Brughera *et al.*, 2013) [Eqs. (6) and (7)]. For the numerical solution, we calculated the integrals as a sum with $-2500 \mu s \leq \tau \leq 2500 \mu s$ in steps of $1 \mu s$.

Figure 8(C) shows the centroid across IPD for different frequencies (cf. Brughera *et al.*, 2013, Fig. (5)). Brughera *et al.* (2013) relate the insertion of the centroid with $9 \mu s$ to the threshold value of $p_c = 0.794$ [shown in Fig. 8(A)]. This relation is equivalent to a linear scaling to d' [see left and right y axis in Fig. 8(C)]. They extracted a ΔITD threshold from an ITD axis (here shown as IPD), so their predictions appear to be off by a factor of 2.

The slope m discussed in this work describes how d' changes over frequency for a fixed IPD; this is equivalent to the change of d' in each vertical cut in Fig. 8(C). For an example IPD of 0.5π rads, the d' values for the five

frequencies in Fig. 8(C) marked by stars are 2.23, 1.77, 1.39, 1.09, and 0.84. Solving Eq. (6) for these values results in a slope of $m \approx 20$ dB/oct. This slope changes over IPD by a few tenths of a dB which is due to the numerical imprecision.

¹See supplementary material at <https://www.scitation.org/doi/suppl/10.1121/10.0015246> for audiograms and results for all subjects.

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